

Event Abstract

Obscure Death: Causes of Unexplained Death

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General background: Obscure death (OD) is a medicolegal dilemma which had not been well covered in the literature.

It could be a real OD if there is no cause was achieved after having all relevant data and conducting a complete standard autopsy followed by a series of complementary investigations. Moreover, it could also be relative OD if one or more of those important procedures or investigations were not performed, whatever were the circumstances.

OD is a multifactorial problem, caused by various factors involved such as cadaveric, autopsy, laboratory, financial, legislation, and local regulations.

In fact, obscurity of death includes undetermined mechanism, cause, and mode of death.

There are a lot of factors or difficulties, which could interact and leads to situation of cul-de-sac i.e., obscure death. However, our present talk is a general discussion.

Keywords: Obscure, death, causes, Libya.

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